

POSTLACTATIONAL ESTRUS REACTION AND SOWS FARROWING RATE IN COLD AND WARM SEASONS*

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SUMMARY: The effects of the warm and cold period of the year on the sows postlactational estrus reaction and farrowing rate, were investigated on an intensive pig production farm unit in Vojvodina. Average weaning-to-estrus interval duration was significantly ($P>0.01$) longer (8.1 vs. 6.0 days) and farrowing rate was significantly ($P>0.05$) lower (72.9% vs. 80.2%) in warm compared with cold season. The present results support the findings of other authors that higher temperature and extended photoperiod, during summer months, are the main factors influencing reduction the reproductive parameters in the breeding sows herds. This phenomenon is known as a "summer sows infertility".

Key words: estrus, fertility, season, sow.

INTRODUCTION

Paragenetic factors, as nutrition, parity structure of the herd, housing, AI technology and general health status of the breeding animals (sows, boars, gilts) has a greater impact on reproductive parameters (Stančić, 2005; Stančić et al., 2010) than genetic factors (breed, race, inbreeding). Because the genetic heritability of all reproductive traits is low, about 10 to 30% (See, 2002).

In the modern production conditions, the phenomenon known as "summer sows infertility" represents the most significant factor that reduced sows fertility parameters. Namely, for as long as 40 years, considerably lower values of sow fertility parameters have been evident in the warmer part of the year (Almond, 1992). Thus, Aumaitre et al. (1976) found significantly lower farrowing rates, extended weaning-to-estrus interval, increased number of irregular rebreeding and the reduced number of live-born pigs per

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litter in the warm part of the year (June – September). This phenomenon is related to the negative effect of increased ambient temperature and daily photoperiod duration on sow reproductive functions (Gordon, 1997; Stančić et al., 2011).

The aim of the present study was to investigate the variation of the postlactational estrus reaction and farrowing rate in the sows, within cold and warm season of the year, at the industrial farm unit in AP Vojvodina (Serbia).

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The reproductive performance parameters (weaning-to-estrus interval, farrowing rate and rebreeding rate), for total of 3062 farrowings within one year, was obtained from reproductive evidence of one big farm unit in AP Vojvodina (Serbia).

During lactation, which lasts approximately 30 days, sows are kept in individual boxes. The nutrition of sows is adequate, with meals prepared for certain categories of breeding sows. Estrus testing is performed in the presence of boar, once within 24h. Artificial insemination is performed with liquid diluted semen, with the doses of 100ml, with approximately 5×10^9 progressive motile spermatozoa. Double insemination was performed: firstly, a couple of hours after estrus detection, and secondly, 24h later. Rebreeding control was conducted in facilities for inseminated (pregnant) sows, starting around 14 days after insemination.

The values of all the above stated parameters of reproductive performance were analyzed in relation to the parity of farrowing and a season of the year. The year is divided in the warm (May to September) and cold (October to April) season.

The obtained results were processed using “Statistika 7” software program.

RESULTS

The average weaning-to-estrus interval (WEI) duration, for all sows, in both of the seasons, was 6.8 days. In the warm season, WEI was significantly ($P > 0.01$) longer (8.1 days) than in the cold season (6.0 days).

Table 1. Weaning-to-estrus interval duration (days)
Tabela 1. Trajanje intervala zalučenje – estrus (dani)

Parity / Paritet	Weaning-to-estrus interval (days) / Interval zalučenje – estrus (dani)					
	Period of year / Period godine				Total / Ukupno	
	Cold / Hladni		Warm / Topli			
	n	$\bar{x}$	n	$\bar{x}$	N	$\bar{x}$
1.	353	7.8 ^a	242	12.5 ^b	595	9.7
2. – 5.	1121	5.4 ^a	922	7.8 ^b	2043	6.4
≥ 6.	238	6.3 ^a	186	8.7 ^b	424	7.1
Total / Ukupno	1712	6.0 ^a	1350	8.1 ^b	3062	6.8

a, bValues with different superscripts, in the same rows, are statistically significantly different ($P > 0.01$).

a, bVrednosti sa različitim superskriptima, u istom redu, se statistički značajno

razlikuju ($P>0,01$).

During the whole year, gilts WEI was longer for about 3 days (average 9.7 days) compared with sows (average 6.8 days). In both gilts and sows, the average WEI was significantly ($P>0.01$) longer in the warm than in the cold period (Table 1).

Farrowing rate was also significantly different ($P>0.05$), after insemination in the first post-lactation estrus, between the cold (80.2%) and warm (72.9%) period of the year, for all parity sows (Table 2).

Table 2. Farrowing rate after insemination in first estrus after weaning

Tabela 2. Vrednost prašenja posle osemenjavanja u prvom estrusu posle zalučenja

Parity / Paritet		Period of year / <i>Period godine</i>		Total / <i>Ukupno</i>
		Cold / <i>Hladni</i>	Warm / <i>Topli</i>	
1.	Inseminated (n) / <i>Osemenjeno (n)</i>	353	242	595
	Farrowed / <i>Oprašeno</i>	n	141	388
		%	70.0 ^A	58.3 ^B
2. – 5.	Inseminated (n) / <i>Osemenjeno (n)</i>	1121	922	2043
	Farrowed / <i>Oprašeno</i>	n	658	1600
		%	84.0 ^a	71.4 ^b
≥ 6.	Inseminated (n) / <i>Osemenjeno (n)</i>	238	186	424
	Farrowed / <i>Oprašeno</i>	n	128	312
		%	77.3 ^a	68.8 ^b
Total / <i>Ukupno</i>	Inseminated (n) / <i>Osemenjeno (n)</i>	1712	1350	3062
	Farrowed / <i>Oprašeno</i>	n	985	2358
		%	80.2 ^a	72.9 ^b

Values with different superscripts, in the same rows, are statistically significantly different.

Vrednosti sa različitim superskriptima, u istom redu, se statistički značajno razlikuju.

^{A,B} ($P>0.01$); ^{a,b} ($P>0.05$).

Gilts achieved a significantly lower ($P>0.01$) farrowing rate in cold (70%) and warm (58.3%), compared with sows (Table 2).

Table 3. Distribution of regular and irregular return rate

Tabela 3. Distribucija regularnih i neregularnih povraćanja

	Period of year / <i>Period godine</i>				Total / <i>Ukupno</i>	
	Cold / <i>Hladni</i>		Warm / <i>Topli</i>			
	n	%	n	%	n	%
Total returne rate / <i>Ukupno povraćanje</i>	339	-	365	-	704	-
Regular returne / <i>Regularno povraćanje</i> ¹	246	72.6 ^A	170	46.6 ^{AB}	416	59.1
Iregulara returne / <i>Neregularno povraćanje</i> ²	93	27.4 ^B	195	53.4 ^{AB}	288	40.9

¹ Within intervals / *U intervalima*: 18 - 24 i 36 - 48 days after AI / dana posle VO.

² Within intervals / *U intervalima*: ≤ 17 , 25 - 35 i ≥ 49 days after AI / dana posle VO.

^{A,B} Values with different superscripts, in the same rows and columns, are statistically significantly different ($P > 0,01$).

^{A,B} *Vrednosti sa različitim superskriptima, unutar istog reda i kolone, se statistički značajno razlikuju ($P > 0,01$).*

It is important to state that the irregular return rate was significantly ($P > 0.01$) higher in the warm (53.4%) than in the cold (27.4%) season. Regular and irregular return rate values, in the cold season, was significantly ($P > 0.01$) different (72.6% vs. 27.4%), both these differences was not significant in the warm season (46.6% vs. 53.4%) (Table 3).

DISCUSSION

Infertility or reduced fertility in sows can be influenced by genetic and paragenetic factors. The most important paragenetic factors are nutrition, housing, parity structure of breeding herds, climatic conditions (ambient temperature and daily photoperiod duration), treatment with hormonal preparations and general health of breeding animals (Tomes et al., 1982; Stančić, 2005). Significant reduction of sow fertility during the warm period of the year, has been reported by numerous authors. This phenomenon is known as “summer or seasonal infertility syndrome” (Love, 1978; Rozeboom et al., 2000; Stančić et al., 2011). Significant reduction of sows fertility parameters (weaning-to-estrus interval duration, farrowing rates, the rebreeding and abortion rates, as well as the average litter size), within warm season, has been reported since 1970s, by Aumaitre et al. (1976). Summer infertility is considerably more prominent in gilts, compared with sows (Britt et al., 1983). Research results by a number of authors, as stated by Gordon (1997), point out the general conclusion that the parameters of sow fertility, during the warm period, are reduced by 15 to 20% compared with the cold period of the year.

The results of the research in this paper showed that the average weaning-to-estrus interval (WEI) duration was significantly higher ($P > 0.01$) within warm (8.1 days), compared with cold season (6.0 days). Very similar differences in WEI duration, between the cold and warm period of the year, were identified also by certain other authors (Aumaitre et al., 1976; Hurtgen et al., 1980; Peltoniemi et al., 1999; Stančić et al., 2002; Almond and Bilkei, 2005). Thus, for instance, in Eastern European countries Almond and Bilkei (2005) ascertained that this interval lasts 5.9 days on average in the cold and 7.8 days in the warm period of the year. The extended duration of WEI reduces reproductive efficiency of breeding herds both directly and indirectly. Firstly, the reproductive efficiency is reduced directly, as sows with extended WEI achieve lower farrowing rates (%) after insemination in the first post-lactation estrus and have a significantly lower number of pigs per litter (Staničić, 1994; Kemp and Soede, 1996; Stančić, 1997a and 1997b; Borchardt Netto, 1998; Stančić et al., 2000; Stančić, 2002; Timotijević et al., 2003). Secondly, the reproductive efficiency is reduced indirectly, as the extended WEI prolongs the interval between successive farrowing and, consequently, reduces the farrowing index, resulting in the reduced yearly pig production and the increased number of non-productive feeding days (Tomes et al., 1982; Tubbs, 1990; Stančić, 2005). According to the research conducted by Prunier et al. (1996), the extended WEI during the warm period of the year is a consequence of the decreased

capability of hypothalamus to re-establish the normal pulsatile secretion of Gn-RH. This inhibits the release of hypophyseal gonadotropin (FSH and LH), which results in postponement of the first post-lactation ovulation and estrus manifestation.

The farrowing rate after insemination in the first post-lactation estrus was also statistically significant ($P>0.01$) lower (72.9%) in the warm than in the cold period of the year (80.2%). The results of other authors also indicate lower values of farrowing during the warm period compared with the cold period of the year. Thus, Almond and Bilkei (2005) determined that this value reaches 91% in the cold and 78% in the warm periods of the year. In this research, the irregular return rate was significantly ($P>0.01$) higher in the warm (53.4%) than in the cold (27.4%) season. The most frequent reason for farrowing failure, i.e. unsuccessful conception (rebreeding, return to estrus), in summer months is irregular rebreedings (i.e. reestablishment of estrus 25 to 35 days or > 46 days after insemination). Such early disruption of pregnancy is a consequence of embryo mortality (Xue et al., 1994) or the regression of pregnancy corpora lutea (CL) (Wrathall et al., 1986). Namely, recent research indicate that high ambient temperature leads to the increased embryo mortality, and consequently, to disruption of pregnancy (Stančić et al., 2004). Besides, it seems that the increased ambient temperature inhibits prolactin (LTH) release from hypophysis, which is necessary for enhancement of secretory activity of pregnancy CL after 16th day of gestation, which causes disruption of pregnancy and irregular rebreeding manifestation (Tast et al., 2002; Kirkwood, 2009). Certain authors point out that the stress induced by increased ambient temperature reduces sows immunity to infectious diseases which causes increased mortality and/or fetal mummification (Yeske, 2007; Givens and Marley, 2008). According to the research of certain authors (Christianson, 1992), abortions were most frequently caused by infectious factors, and less frequently by stress induced by increased ambient temperature.

The phenomenon of seasonal infertility in sows is very complex. Precise mechanisms of physiological basis of this phenomenon are not entirely clarified (Kirkwood, 2009). However, the results of all the research consistently indicate that the reduced fertility in sows is a consequence of the interaction of high ambient temperature and extended daily photoperiod in the warm period of the year. These factors act through neuroendocrine mechanisms at the level of cerebral nervous system – hypothalamus – hypophysis – ovary (Tast, 2002).

The results of the present research, clearly indicate that the values of the examined parameters of sow fertility are significantly lower during the warm period compared with the cold period of the year. Additionally, these parameters point to significantly more prominent decrease in gilts than in sows.

CONCLUSION

Obtained results clearly indicate that there are negative effects of the warm period of the year on the examined parameters of sow fertility:

During the warm period the sows weaning-to-estrus interval duration was statistically significantly higher (8.1 days) compared with cold period of the year (6.0 days).

The farrowing rate, after insemination in the first post-lactation estrus, during the warm period is statistically lower (72.9%) compared with the cold period (80.2%).

The irregular return rate was significantly higher in the warm (53.4%) than in the cold (27.4%) season.

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POSTLAKTACIJSKO ESTRUSNO REAGOVANJE I VREDNOST PRAŠENJA KRMAČA U TOPLOJ I HLADNOJ SEZONI

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Izvod

Ispitivan je uticaj toplog i hladnog perioda godine na postlaktacijsko estrusno reagovanje i vrednost prašenja na jednoj velikoj farmi za proizvodnju svinja u AP Vojvodini (Srbija). Prosečno trajanje intervala zalučenje-estrus je bilo statistički značajno ($P>0.01$) duže (8 dana) u toplom, u odnosu na hladni period godine (6 dana). Vrednost prašenja, posle osemenjavanja u prvom postlaktacijskom estrusu, bila je statistički značajno ($P>0.01$) niža (72.9%) od one u hladnom periodu godine (80.2%). Dobijeni rezultati potvrđuju nalaze drugih autora, da povišena ambijentalna temperatura i produžen dnevni fotoperiod, tokom toplih letnjih meseci, značajno redukuju vrednosti parametara reproduktivne performanse krmača. Ovaj fenomen je poznat kao „letnji infertilitet krmača“.

Ključne reči: estrus, fertilitet, sezona, krmača.

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